

Three simple visible spectrophotometric methods for the assay of cetirizine

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Three simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods (A-C) for the assay of cetirizine (as dihydrochloride, CET) are proposed. Methods A and B are based on the formation of ion-association complex involving carboxylic acid group of CET and the basic dyes, safranin-O (SFN-O, method A), methylene blue (MB, method B). Method C is based on the involvement of tertiary amino group in drug with α,γ -aconitic anhydride (dehydration product of citric acid-acetic anhydride) as coloured internal salt. The methods are suitable for the assay of cetirizine in pharmaceutical formulations.

Cetirizine is an antihistaminic and is chemically known as acetic acid, [2-[4-[(4-chlorophenyl)phenylmethyl]-1-piperazinyl]ethoxy]-, dihydrochloride. It is official in BP¹, EP². The methods so far reported for the estimation of CET include HPLC³⁻⁸, TLC⁹, HPTLC¹⁰ and spectrophotometric (UV¹¹, visible^{12,13}). Even though extraction spectrophotometric procedures are popular for their sensitivity in the assay of drug, there are only two reports using acidic dyes (bromo cresol green and alizarin red S)^{12,13} for the determination of CET, in pure and pharmaceutical formulations. During the course of our studies to develop sensitive visible spectrophotometric methods, it was observed that the analytically useful carboxylic acid and tertiary amino groups in CET have not been properly exploited. CET being acidic in nature due to the presence of carboxylic acid group forms an ion-association complex with the basic dye (SFN-O, method A or MB, method B) which is extractable into chloroform. Method C is based on the coloured internal salt formation with involvement of tertiary amino group in CET and dehydration product of citric acid (aconitic anhydride) when treated with citric acid (Ci) and acetic anhydride (Ac₂O). The results are statistically validated.

Results and discussion

In order to establish the optimum pH range for methods A and B, the CET was allowed to react with the respective dye in aqueous solution at pH 8.0–11.0 using NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer. The complex formed was extracted into chloroform for absorbance measurement. The results show that a quantitative extraction was made at a pH 9.0–10.0. All subsequent studies were carried out at pH 9.8 for both the methods. A 1.0 ml portion of pH 9.8 buffer solution was

found to be optimal. The maximum shaking time was determined by varying the shaking time from 3–8 min, although 4 min was sufficient, prolonged shaking has no adverse effect on the extraction and 5 min was selected for this study. A ratio of 1 : 1 (methods A and B) of organic to aqueous phases were required for efficient extraction of the coloured species and lowest reagent blank reading. It was found that better reproducibility and a lowest reagent blank was achieved if the dye was purified by extraction with chloroform initially. In order to establish optimum experimental

Table 1. Optical characteristics, precision and accuracy of the proposed methods for CET

Parameters	Method A	Method B	Method C
λ_{max} (nm)	520	650	580
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.6–20	4.5–50	0.7–6.0
Molar absorptivity ($\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.46×10^4	5.19×10^3	3.32×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2/0.001$ absorbance unit)	0.031	0.088	0.014
Optimum photometric range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	8.91–12.30	15.48–33.11	2.23–4.78
Regression equation ($y = a + bc$) ^a			
Slope (b)	0.032	0.011	0.072
Intercept (a)	0.0005	0.0013	–0.0007
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9997	0.9998	0.9999
Standard error of estimation (S_e)	3.16×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-3}	1.81×10^{-3}
Relative standard deviation (%) ^b	0.627	0.860	0.646
% Error in bulk sample	0.263	0.294	–0.347

^a $Y = a + bc$, where c is the concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$. ^bAverage of six determinations considered.

Table 2. Determination of CET in pharmaceutical formulations

Pharmaceutical sample (Labelled amount)	Amount found by proposed methods ^a			Reference ^b method	%Recovery by proposed methods ^c		
	Method A	Method B	Method C		Method A	Method B	Method C
Syrup I (1 mg)	1.01 ± 0.007 <i>F</i> = 1.78 <i>t</i> = 0.64	0.97 ± 0.010 <i>F</i> = 1.90 <i>t</i> = 0.55	1.08 ± 0.007 <i>F</i> = 2.19 <i>t</i> = 1.07	0.99 ± 0.010	99.99 ± 0.79	100.03 ± 0.76	100.10 ± 0.71
Tablet II (5 mg)	5.02 ± 0.047 <i>F</i> = 1.23 <i>t</i> = 0.54	5.01 ± 0.047 <i>F</i> = 1.63 <i>t</i> = 0.31	5.04 ± 0.042 <i>F</i> = 1.06 <i>t</i> = 0.90	5.02 ± 0.042	100.54 ± 0.94	100.55 ± 1.08	100.50 ± 0.87
Tablet III (10 mg)	9.99 ± 0.062 <i>F</i> = 3.25 <i>t</i> = 1.22	9.96 ± 0.062 <i>F</i> = 3.16 <i>t</i> = 0.90	9.95 ± 0.052 <i>F</i> = 2.3 <i>t</i> = 1.67	9.96 ± 0.034	99.93 ± 0.62	99.80 ± 0.61	99.90 ± 0.52
Capsule IV (10 mg)	9.95 ± 0.105 <i>F</i> = 2.09 <i>t</i> = 0.31	9.99 ± 0.106 <i>F</i> = 2.82 <i>t</i> = 0.45	9.96 ± 0.104 <i>F</i> = 2.06 <i>t</i> = 0.48	9.94 ± 0.073	99.54 ± 1.05	99.50 ± 1.22	99.61 ± 1.04

^aAverage ± standard deviation of six determinations; the *t*- and *F*-values refer to comparison of the proposed method with the reference method. Theoretical values at 95% confidence limit, *t* = 2.57, *F* = 5.05.

^bReference method (CET¹¹).

^cAfter adding 3 different amounts of the pure labelled to the pharmaceutical formulation, each value is an average of 3 determinations.

conditions for method C, the effect of parameters such as volume of citric acid-acetic anhydride (Ci-Ac₂O) solution, heating time for maximum colour formation and stability of coloured species were studied. Optimum volumes 9–11 ml of Ci-Ac₂O solution was found to be adequate. 10 ml of Ci-Ac₂O reagent and heating for 30 min on a boiling water bath were found to be necessary for maximum colour development (λ_{\max} 580 nm).

The optimum conditions for the colour development of method were established by varying the parameters one at a time, keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the coloured species.

The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity for each method are given in Table 1. The precision of each method was found by measuring absorbances of six replicate samples containing known amounts of drug and the results obtained are incorporated in Table 1. Regression analysis using the method of least squares was made to evaluate the slope (*b*), intercept (*a*), correlation coefficient (*r*) and standard error of estimation (*S_e*) for each method and are presented in Table 1. The accuracy of each method was ascertained by comparing the results by proposed and reference methods (UV) statistically by the *t*- and *F*-tests (Table 2). This comparison shows that there is no significant difference between the results of proposed methods and those of the reference ones. The similarity of the results is an obvious evidence that during the application of these methods, the additives and excipients

that are usually present in tablets or syrup do not interfere in the assay of proposed methods. As an additional check of accuracy of the proposed methods, recovery experiments were performed by adding a fixed amount of the drug to the preanalysed formulations. The percent recoveries were found to be within 1%.

Experimental

A Milton Roy Spectronic 1201 and Systronics 106 digital spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched quartz cells were used for the spectral and absorbance measurements. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

All the chemicals and reagents were of A.R. grade and the solutions were prepared in triply distilled water. Aqueous solutions of SFN-O (Fluka, 2.857 × 10⁻⁴ M), MB (Fluka, 3.12 × 10⁻⁴ M), and NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer of pH 9.8 were prepared for methods A and B. Citric acid-Ac₂O solution (6.245 × 10⁻¹ M) was prepared by dissolving 12 g of citric acid monohydrate (B.D.H.) in 5 ml of anhydrous methanol and diluting upto 100 ml with acetic anhydride (B.D.H.) for method C. The standard stock solution of CET (1 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of drug in 100 ml of distilled water. The working standard solutions were prepared by further dilution of the stock solution with distilled water, 80 µg/ml for method A, 200 µg/ml for method B. For method C, 1 mg/ml stock solution of CET was prepared by dissolving 50 mg in 50 ml of chloroform. The stock solution was washed with 2 × 5.0 ml portions of 5% sodium carbonate solution and the chloroformic solution

was diluted further with chloroform to obtain the working standard solution of concentration (free base form, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) for method C. Sample solutions for formulations (Tablets or syrup) were prepared exactly in the same manner as given under the standard solutions with prior filtration before making up to volume and analysed as described for pure samples.

Procedures :

Methods A and B : To a series of 125 ml separating funnels containing aliquots of standard CET solution [0.5–2.5 ml, 80 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (method A) and 0.5–2.5 ml, 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (method B)], 1 ml of pH 9.8 buffer and 5.0 ml of dye solution SFN-O (method A) or MB (method B) were added. The total volume of aqueous phase in each separating funnel was adjusted to 10 ml with distilled water and 10 ml of CHCl_3 was added. The contents were shaken for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the absorbance of the separated organic layer was measured at 520 nm (method A) or 650 nm (method B) against a similar reagent blank. The amount of CET in methods A and B were computed from their respective calibration curves.

Method C : Aliquots of standard chloroformic CET (free base form) solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were transferred into a series of 25 ml graduated tubes and gently evaporated on a water-bath to dryness. 10 ml of citric acid-acetic anhydride reagent was added to each tube. The tubes were placed in a boiling water-bath and heated for 30 min. The solution in each tube was made upto the mark with Ac_2O . The absorbance of the coloured solutions were mea-

sured at 580 nm after 15 min against a reagent blank prepared in a similar way. The amount of CET was deduced from the calibration curve.

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